

AGRICULTURE
ARCHIVES

OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL

Check for updates

Citation: Ismail E., Radwa B. Ahmed, Aalaaa A. Aboelkassem, Rehab Ashraf, Safaa Elghaity, Reda Abdo and Haitham M. A. Elsayed. (2023). Response of early seedling inbred lines of wheat against 20% PEG6000 induced condition. Agriculture Archives: An International Journal. V02i01.25-31. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7731454>

DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7731454>

Corresponding Author:
Haitham M. A. Elsayed
dhaithamm@yahoo.com

Received on: November 23, 2022
Revised on: January 17, 2023
Accepted on: January 28, 2023

Copyright: © 2023 Haitham M. A. Elsayed. Published under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) (CC BY 4.0) license.

ORIGINAL RESEARCH ARTICLE

Response of early seedling inbred lines of wheat against 20% PEG6000 induced condition

Ismail E.¹, Radwa B. Ahmed², Aalaaa A. Aboelkassem², Rehab Ashraf², Safaa Elghaity², Reda Abdo² and Haitham M. A. Elsayed*¹

¹Department of Genetics, Faculty of. Agriculture, Sohag University, Sohag, 82786-Egypt

²Bitechnology Branch, Faculty of. Agriculture, Sohag University, Sohag, 82786-Egypt

ABSTRACT

At the germination and seedling stages, the drought resistance of six genotypes of winter wheat was investigated under lab condition. PEG6000 was employed in research under controlled circumstances to simulate drought stress at 20% concentration. Our finding showed that the inbred lines (Sakha-94 x Misr-1) and (Weiber x Sids-12) demonstrated highest drought tolerant. In order to achieve high yield under water stress, these lines have a great deal of potential to be incorporated with the current commercial wheat types.

Keywords: Wheat Lines, Germination, PEG6000

INTRODUCTION

Seed germination, the first stage of growth, is susceptible to water scarcity because soil moisture at the time of planting may hinder seedling emergence, which in turn affects yield output. Due to a water deficit, plant physiological and biochemical processes as well as growth and development may all be significantly impacted. The plant integrates a variety of responses and adaptive mechanisms at the morphological, physiological, and molecular levels to respond to drought stress. Yet, the use of these systems varies significantly between different plant species or genotypes within a species. When there is a water shortage early on plants, typically have the capacity to efficiently absorb water from the soil through their root systems, partly close their stomata to reduce water loss through transpiration, and change their metabolism to accommodate the available carbon resource. Prolines, soluble sugars, spermines, and betaine are examples of osmolytic substances that build in plant cells as stress levels rise to maintain the cell turgor pressure. Therefore, the physical and molecular reactions that occur when plants respond to drought involve a variety of biological macro and micro molecules, including nucleic acids (DNA, RNA, and microRNA), proteins, carbohydrates, lipids, hormones, ions, free radicals, and mineral elements.

Due to PEG₆₀₀₀ high molecular weight it is used for seedling stage selection for drought tolerance genotypes . PEG₆₀₀₀ molecules are too large to be absorbed by plants, too small to affect osmotic potential, and even too massive to be anticipated to quickly penetrate intact plant tissues . Because PEG does not penetrate the apoplast, water is withdrawn from the cell, making PEG₆₀₀₀ solution more like dry soil than other solutions.

The goal of this study was to determine whether there were differences in the responses of six winter wheat inbred lines to water stress in order to be grown in marginal and dry land by estimating several morphological drought resistance parameters under PEG₆₀₀₀ as a water deficiency at early seedling stage.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Six wheat genotypes made up the experimental materials for this investigation (Table 1). The seeds were collected from Genetics Dept., Faculty of Agric., Sohag Univ., Sohag, Egypt. These genotypes were directly seeded in moisten petri dishes, and their drought tolerance and various root and shoot characteristics were assessed over the interval of three replications.

Table 1: List of wheat inbred lines used for present investigation.

Lines No.	Lines Source
1	Misr-1 X Sids-12
2	Weiber X Sids-12
3	Katela X Sakha-94
4	Weiber X Misr-1
5	Katela X Sids-12
6	Sakha-94 X Misr-1

Mean performance was recorded for seedling length, root numbers, seedling fresh weight, seedling dry weight, germination percentage, vigor index and tissue water content.

Preparation of Priming Solution

Drought-stressed plants were watered daily with a 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ solution (dissolving 20 gm of PEG₆₀₀₀ in 100 ml of purified water), which was applied for 15 days.

Seed Placement for Germination

The surface of each seed was sterilised with 5% sodium hybochloride solution for 20 mins, followed by a sterile water rinse and room temperature air drying. The priming media was made in 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ solution and distilled water, and it was primed for nine hours. Seeds that had been soaked were then air dried and put in petridish. For each replicate, 15 seeds were put in a petri dish with a diameter of 90 cm, layered

with filter paper moistened with 10 ml of 20% PEG₆₀₀₀, and exposed to conditions that included a photoperiod of 114 hours, 250 μmole⁻²s⁻¹ day/night temperature of 25 °C, and a relative humidity of 60/75%.

Experimental Design

Three replications were used in the experiment's Complete Randomized Design (CRD). The eximend wheat lines presented in (Table 1) under primed seed with 20% PEG6000 solution.

Recording Data

Considering the data collection for different parameters, the mean data of seedling length, root numbers, Seedling fresh weight, seedling dry weight, germination percentage, vigor index and tissue water content were recorded after 15 days of planting seeds. In each petri dishes ten seedlings were evaluated. Shoot and root length of single seedling were measured using a ruler and metre scale two weeks after seeding. After that, each seedling's roots were numbered. The seedling's shoot and root were then dried for 48 hours, and their dry weights were registered using an electric scale.

Statistical Analysis

The collected CRD design data was used to statistically analysis by Excel software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The process and trait of plant drought resistance is quite complicated. Drought resistance in plants is correlated with a number of activities at specific developmental stages, including stomatal movement, photosynthesis, cell osmotic regulation, synthesis of protective macromolecules, and antioxidant synthesis. Plant growth and development are typically quite vulnerable to water sacrificial mechanisms it might cause significant increase in electrolyte leakage from leaves. Keeping a high water content gave researchers the chance to study physiological processes both during droughts and after rehydrating plants. When there is a water shortage in early plants stage, typically have the capacity to efficiently absorb water from the soil through their root systems, partially close their

stomata to limit water loss through transpiration, and change their metabolism to adapt the available carbon resource. Consequently, determining drought resistance is significantly harder and more complicated than determining other stress resistances .

Mean values regarding seedling length under 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ are presented in Fig. 1. The highest seedling length was recorded in (Sakha-94 X Misr-1) reported that when the seeds were induced with a 10% PEG₆₀₀₀ solution, the highest seedling length of wheat was secured..

Fig. 1: Effect of 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ on Seedling Length of tested wheat inbred lines (all means [± S.E.] are significantly different at P<0.05).

When plants are subjected to drought stress in the soil, the roots become the first organ to experience. According to the presented investigation, the majority of the examined inbred lines were affected by drought stress as exhibited in Fig. 2 stated that an important factor in determining a plant’s capacity to extract essential resources from the soil, such as water and mobile nutrients, is the distribution of roots, particularly those that can reach deeper into the soil. Hence, root architecture has a significant impact on the development and productivity of crop plants.

Fig. 2: Effect of 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ on Root Numbers of tested wheat inbred lines (all means [± S.E.] are significantly different at P<0.05).

Germination percentage significantly affected by 20% level PEG₆₀₀₀ resulted declined progressively under 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ in all six inbred lines. The inbred line (Katela X Sakha-94) demonstrated the highest level of tolerance, and the rate of decline was low relative to the other lines (Fig. 3.). Similar to this, found that 25% PEG induced a distract reduction, while 19% PEG caused a reduction in germination percentage, which refer to early seedling germination stage water deficit stress causes delayed and reduced germination. This is consistent with research, which found that at low moisture levels, germination percentage and seedling growth both decreased.

Fig. 3: Effect of 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ on Germination Percentage of tested wheat inbred lines (all means [± S.E.] are significantly different at P<0.05).

Seedling fresh and dry weights were significantly decreased under 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ (Fig. 4 and 5). The seedling fresh weight was highest in (Weiber X Sids-12) and (Sakha-94 X Misr-1). While, the variation in seedling dry weight was observed, and the results showed that (Katela X Sakha-94) was constantly decreased value, that is caused by the treatment. And So far, other genotypes reacted to the observations in various ways. reported that when osmotic potential increased, the fresh weight of seedlings of both drought-tolerant and sensitive durum wheat genotypes decreased. Numerous other scientists have noted the declining trend in seedling fresh and dry weight, who showed that the fresh and dried weight of seedlings was significantly impacted by water stress.

The vigor index and tissue water content values were affected by the level of 20% PEG₆₀₀₀. The highest vigor index were presented in (Sakha-94 x Misr-1) (Fig. 6). Meanwhile, the values regarding tissue water content responded differently to the

observations (Fig. 7). illustrated that seedling vigor traits and tissue water content decreased with increasing of PEG and NaCl concentrations. reported that wheat seedlings under drought stress had considerably decreased growth vigour.

Fig. 4: Effect of 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ on Seedling Fresh Weight of tested wheat inbred lines (all means [± S.E.] are significantly different at P<0.05).

Fig. 5: Effect of 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ on Seedling Dry Weight of tested wheat inbred lines (all means [± S.E.] are significantly different at P<0.05).

Fig. 6: Effect of 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ on Vigor Index of tested wheat inbred lines (all means [± S.E.] are significantly different at P<0.05).

Fig. 7: Effect of 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ on Tissue Water Content of tested wheat inbred lines (all means [± S.E.] are significantly different at P<0.05).

Studies of correlation between several variables (Table 2) revealed a favourable and highly significant relationship between seedling length and vigour index. Our study found a strong correlation between the characteristics we provided, suggesting that increasing seedling length would likewise boost vigour index. In addition, root numbers with seedling dry weight and seedling fresh weight with vigor index showed positive and significant correlation. Similar results were obtained in they noticed a correlation between seedling length and germination rate. Additionally, a number of studies have shown that the drought reaction of seedlings and the drought response of mature plants were fairly well correlated. Besides that, there was a fair amount of correlation between the drought responses of adult plants and seedlings.

To evaluate the degree of similarity and dissimilarity among examined genotypes against induced 20% PEG₆₀₀₀, the Euclidean Similarity Index was used (Fig. 8.). The results indicated two clusters. The first cluster illustrates (Sakha-94 x Misr-1), (Katela x Sids-12) and (Weiber x Misr-1). Meanwhile, the second cluster viewed (Weiber x Sids-12), (Katela x Sakha-94) and (Misr-1 x Sids-12). These clusters had a stable performance in 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ stress, which provides visibility performance response during the experiment. Therefore, similarity index (Euclidean) was used to identify superior tolerant genotypes under salinity stress conditions for accuracy and reliability index (Shamim et al., 2014).

Percentage, Seedling Fresh and Dry Weight, Vigor Index and Tissue Water Content under 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ condition.

Table 2: Pearson correlation matrix among studied parameters.

	Seedling Length	Root Numbers	Seedling Fresh Weight	Seedling Dry Weight	Germination Percentage	Vigor Index
Root Numbers	0.312					
Seedling Fresh Weight	0.689	0.594				
Seedling Dry Weight	0.317	0.771*	0.472			
Germination Percentage	-0.165	0.412	0.267	-0.120		
Vigor Index	0.990**	0.390	0.744*	0.321	-0.024	
Tissue Water Content	0.464	0.251	0.645	-0.211	0.709	0.567

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Overall, our finding showed that the inbred lines (Sakha-94 x Misr-1) and (Weiber x Sids-12) demonstrated highest drought tolerant because they did not statistically significantly reduced under 20% PEG₆₀₀₀.

Fig. 8: Paired group (UPGMA), similarity index (Euclidean) of six wheat inbred lines based on Seedling Length, Root Numbers, Germination

CONCLUSION

In regard to the previously mentioned findings from the current study, it’s possible to conclude that 20% PEG₆₀₀₀ osmotic stress has a positive significant effect at early seedling growth, which helps to promote wheat seed germination and seedling growth in drought-stressed conditions.

Consent and Ethical Approval

As per university standard guideline, participant consent and ethical approval have been collected and preserved by the authors.

Competing interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests

exist.

Authors’ Contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by the Genetics Dept., Faculty of Agric., Sohag Univ., Sohag, Egypt.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Mwale, S., Hamusimbi, C., & Mwansa, K. (2003). Germination, emergence and growth of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) in response to osmotic seed priming. *Seed Sci. Technol.* 31: 199-206.
- [2.] Van den Berg, L. & Zeng, Y. J. (2006). Response of South African indigenous grass species to drought stress induced by polyethylene glycol (PEG) 6000. *Afr. J. Bot.* 72: 284-286.
- [3.] Osborne, S. L., Schepers, V., Francis, D. D., & Schlemmer, M. R. (2002). Use of spectral radiance to estimate in-season biomass and grain yield in nitrogen and water-stressed crop. *Crop Sci.*, 42: 165–171.
- [4.] Chaniago, Irawati, Auzar, Syarif, & Putri, Riviona. (2017). Sorghum Seedling Drought Response: In Search of Tolerant Genotypes. *International Journal on advanced Science Engineering Information Technology.* 7(3): 892-897.
- [5.] Reddy, A. R., Chaitanya, K. V., & Vivekanandan, M. (2004). Drought induced responses of photosynthesis and antioxidant metabolism in higher plants. *J. Plant Physiol.* 161: 1189–1202.

- [6.] Hu, H., & Xiong, L. (2014). Genetic engineering and breeding of drought resistant crops. *Annu. Rev. Plant Biol.* 65: 715–741.
- [7.] Seki, M., Umezawa, T., Urano, K., & Shinozaki, K. (2007). Regulatory metabolic networks in drought stress responses. *Curr. Opin. Plant Biol.* 10: 296–302.
- [8.] Ingram, J., & Bartels, D. (1996). The Molecular basis of dehydration tolerance in plants. *Annu. Rev. Plant Physiol. Plant Mol. Biol.* 47: 337-403.
- [9.] Jatoi, S. A., Latif, M. M., Arif, M., Ahson, M., Khan, A. & Siddiqui, S. U. (2014). Comparative assessment of wheat landraces against polyethylene glycol simulated drought stress. *Sci. Tech. and Dev.* 33: 1-6.
- [10.] Carpita, N., Sabularse D., Mofezinos D. & Delmer D. (1979). Determination of the pore size of cell walls of living plant cells. *Sci.* 205:114-117. Veslues, P., Ober, E. & Sharp, R. (1998). Root growth and oxygen relations at low water potentials: Impact of oxygen availability in polyethylene glycol solutions. *Plant Physiol.* 116:1403-1412.
- [11.] Agrawal, R. (2003). Seed Technology. *Newdehli India: Pub. co. Ltd.*
- [12.] Oukarroum, A., El Madidi, S., Schansker, G., & Strasser, R. J. (2007). Probing the responses of barley cultivars (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) by chlorophyll a fluorescence OLKJIP under drought stress and rewatering. *Environ. Exp. Bot.* 60: 438–446.
- [13.] Levitt, J. (1980). Responses of plants to environmental stresses, vol II. Water, radiation, salt, and other stresses. *London: Academic Press.*
- [14.] Ahmad, S. Nariman, Shadia, H. S. Kareem, Kamil, M. Mustafa, & Dastan, A. Ahmad. (2017). Early screening of some Kurdistan wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) cultivars under drought stress. *Journal of Agricultural Science.* 9(2):88-103.
- [15.] Baque, A., Nahar, M., Yeasmin, M., Quamruzzaman, M., Rahman, A., Azad, M. J., & Biswas, P. K. (2016). Germination behavior of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) as influenced by polyethylene glycol (PEG). *Universal J. Agril. Res.*4(3):86-91.
- [16.] Fenta, B. A., Beebe, S. E., Kunert, K. J., Burrige, J. D., Barlow, K. M., Lynch, J. P., & Foyer, C. H. (2014). Field Phenotyping of Soybean Roots for Drought Stress Tolerance. *Agronomy.* 4: 418-435.
- [17.] Ashraf, C. M., & Abu-Shakra, S. (1978). Wheat seed germination under low temperature and moisture stress. *Agron. J.* 70: 135-139.
- [18.] Sayar, R., Bchini, H., Mosbahi, M., & Khemira, H. (2010). Response of durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.) growth to salt and drought stresses. *Czech J. Genet. Plant Breed.*, 46: 54-63.
- [19.] Chachar, M., Chachar, N., Chachar, S., Chachar, Q., Mujtaba, S., & Yousafzai, A. (2014). *In vitro* screening technique for drought tolerance of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) genotypes at early seedling stage. *Journal of Agricultural Technology.* 10(6): 1439-1450.
- [20.] Kamran, M., Muhammad, S., Muhammad, A., & Nudrat, A. Aisha. (2009). Alleviation of drought induced adverse effects in spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) using proline as a pre-sowing seed treatment. *Pak. J. Bot.* 41(2):621-632.
- [21.] Moucheshi, A., Heidari, B., & Assad, M. (2012). Alleviation of drought stress effects on wheat using arbuscular mycorrhizal symbiosis. *International Journal of Agriculture Science.* 2(1): 35-47.
- [22.] Hassan, Abdul AL-Razak, Ali, AL-Saady. (2015). Germination and Growth of Wheat Plants (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Under Salt Stress. *Journal of Pharmaceutical, Chemical and Biological Sciences.* 3(3):416-420.
- [23.] El-Hamamsy, M. A. Sam, & Behairy, T. Rehab. (2015). Effect of Salinity Stress on Seedling Vigor and Biochemical Characters of Egyptian Barley Landraces (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). *Middle East Journal of Applied Sciences.* 5(3):786-796.
- [24.] Alamri, A. Saud, Manzer, H. Siddiqui, Mutahhar, Y. Al-Khaishani, & Hayssam, M. Ali. (2018). Response of salicylic acid on seed germination and physio-biochemical changes of wheat under salt stress. *Acta Scientific Agriculture.* 2(5):36-42.
- [25.] Biesaga-Kościelniak, J., Ostrowska, A., Filek, M., Dziurka, M., Waligórski, P., Mirek, M., & Kościelniak, J. (2014). Evaluation of spring wheat (20 varieties) adaptation to soil drought during seedlings growth stage. *Agriculture.* 4: 96-112.

- [26.] Ahmad, N., Khan, M. I., Ahmed, S., Javed, S. B., Faisal, M., Anis, M., Rehman, S., & Umair, S. M. (2013). Change in total phenolic content and antibacterial activity in regenerants of *Vitex negundo* L. *Acta Physiol. Plant.* 35: 791-800.
- [27.] Salim, M. H., Todd, G. W., & Stutte, C. A. (1969). Evaluation of techniques for measuring drought avoidance in cereal seedlings. *Agron. J.* 61:182-185.
- [28.] Sammons, D. J., Peters, D. B., & Hymowitz, T. (1978). Screening soybeans for drought tolerance. I. Growth chamber procedure. *Crop Sci.* 18:1050-1055.
- [29.] Boubaker, M., & Yamada, T. (1995). Differential genotypic responses of string wheat early growth to limited moisture conditions. *Tropicultura.* 13(2):50-53.
- [30.] Ahmed, B. Radwa, Aalaaa, A. Aboelkassem, Shima, M. Ali, Ismail, E., Galal, A. R. El-Sherbeny, & Haitham, M. A. Elsayed. (2019). Screening the Responsible Impact of Fourteen Bread Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Genotypes against Osmotic Water Stress Mediated through PEG₆₀₀₀ in Terms of Seed Germination and Early Seedling Growth Stage in Search of Promising Drought Tolerant Genotypes under in vitro Condition. *Asian Journal of Research in Biosciences.* 1(2): 78-97. Article no.AJORIB.172.